

Gender differences in research method usage in Library and Information Science

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Introduction

In scientific research, the research methodology is a crucial strategy and tool for resolving problems. Existing studies have identified gender differences in the research method usage, i.e., female authors are more likely to use qualitative methods and male authors prefer to use quantitative methods, which can facilitate an in-depth assessment of the influence of gender on knowledge creation in scientific fields (Nunkoo et al., 2020). This study examines gender disparities in the research method usage in the domain of Library and Information Science (LIS) according to author-gender combinations to explore the impact of gender on research method usage.

Methodology

Dataset

The data of this study is based on 5, 281 research articles published from 1990 to 2019 in three core journals in LIS, namely *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (JASIST)*, *Journal of Documentation (JDoc)*, and *Library and Information Science Research (LISR)*. There are 3, 537 articles from *JASIST*, 1, 102 articles from *JDoc*, and 642 articles from *LISR*. The total number of authors for all articles is 12, 135.

Classification of research methods

Table 1. Usage frequency of research methods

No.	Research method	Number of Articles
1	Bibliometrics	870
2	Content analysis	899
3	Delphi study	16
4	Ethnography/field study	88
5	Experiment	1, 314
6	Focus groups	89
7	Historical method	122
8	Interview	690
9	Observation	218
10	Questionnaire	912
11	Research diary/journal	50
12	Theoretical approach	989
13	Think aloud protocol	113
14	Transaction log analysis	260
15	Webometrics	143
16	Other methods	129

Existing studies mainly used content analysis to classify the research methods of an article, which is a time-consuming and arduous task. Inspired by CogLTX (Ding et al., 2020), this paper constructs a classification model CogFT (Cognize Full Texts), which can automatically locate descriptions of research methods from the full text and identify the specific category of research methods. The training set is 1981 articles published in *JASIST*, *JDoc*, and *LISR* from 2001 to 2010 manually annotated with the research methods by Chu & Ke (2017). The model's F₁ value is greater than 85%. Table 1 displays the usage frequency of different research methods.

Inference of author gender

We infer all authors' gender types in each article. The inference of authors' gender is divided into two steps. The first step is to match the authors' gender based on the three following open-source datasets:

- 1) Popular Baby Names (<https://www.ssa.gov/oact/babynames/limits.html>),
- 2) Genni + Ethnea for the Author-ity 2009 dataset (<https://experts.illinois.edu/en/datasets/genni-ethnea-for-the-author-ity-2009-dataset-2>) and
- 3) World Gender Name Dictionary 1.0 (<https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/YPRQH8>).

The second step is to infer the remaining authors' gender via network retrieval, which entails designing search strategies using the author's name, affiliation, or email and then looking up the author's profile, profile photo, or evaluations from other people on search engines and academic websites including Bing, ResearchGate, GoogleScholar, etc.

Measurement of gender differences in research method usage

We select polynomial logistic regression to measure the gender differences in research method usage according to author-gender combinations and utilize odds ratio(OR) to depict the odds that various categories of author-gender combinations use a method compared to a reference category.

$$odds = p/(1 - p) \quad (1)$$

$$OR = odds_c / odds_r \quad (2)$$

Where p is the probability that a category of author-gender combination uses a method, $odds_r$ is the odds that the reference category uses a method, and $odds_c$ is the odds that a category of author-gender combination different from the reference category uses a method.

Results

Statistics of author-gender combinations

The author-gender combination involved in this study is focused on the author team of a single article.

Author-gender combinations can be divided into solo female author (F), solo male author (M), all-female team (FF), mixed-gender team (FM), and all-male team (MM). Table 2 shows the usage frequency of different author-gender combinations.

Table 2. Research method usage by author-gender combinations.

Author-gender combinations	F	M	FF	FM	MM
Usage frequency of methods	1024	1229	631	2519	1490
Ratio (%)	14.86	17.83	9.15	36.54	21.61

Gender differences in research method usage

We employ polynomial logistic regression to compare single-author and multi-author teams separately, and the findings are presented in Tables 3 and 4. The reference categories are M and MM.

As is shown in Table 3, Interview is 2.528 times more likely to be used by solo female authors than solo male authors. Similarly, solo female authors are more likely than solo male authors to use Observation, Questionnaire, Research diary/journal and Think aloud protocol ($OR > 1$, $p < 0.05$). On the contrary, when compared to solo female authors, solo male authors are more likely to use Bibliometrics, Experiment, Historical method, and Theoretical approach ($OR < 1$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 3. Comparison of methods usage between F and M.

Research method	OR (category = F)
Bibliometrics	0.345**
Content analysis	1.007
Delphi study	0.143
Ethnography/field study	1.625
Experiment	0.635*
Focus groups	1.200
Historical method	0.467*
Interview	2.528**
Observation	2.400**
Questionnaire	1.528*
Research diary/journal	5.000*
Theoretical approach	0.418**
Think aloud protocol	4.500*
Transaction log analysis	1.310
Webometrics	0.640
Other methods	1.050

Notes: The reference category is M. OR = Odds Ratio. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .001$

Table 4 shows that FF teams are 1.721 times more likely to use Interview than MM teams. MM teams

are significantly more likely to use Bibliometrics than FF teams by about 13 times ($1 / OR = 1 / 0.075 \approx 13$). Among the 15 methods listed (Delphi study was deleted due to the large standard error), 11 methods are more likely to be used by FM teams than MM teams.

Table 4. Comparison of methods usage between FF, FM, and MM

Research method	OR	
	FF	FM
Bibliometrics	0.075**	1.010
Content analysis	0.661*	2.006**
Ethnography/field study	2.333	4.333*
Experiment	0.145**	1.283**
Focus groups	1.538	3.385**
Historical method	0.273*	1.818
Interview	1.721**	3.676**
Observation	1.478	3.304**
Questionnaire	0.900	2.667**
Research diary/journal	2.750	4.250*
Theoretical approach	0.241**	1.359*
Think aloud protocol	0.824	2.882**
Transaction log analysis	0.321**	2.321**
Webometrics	0.208**	0.917
Other methods	0.586	1.448

Notes: The reference category is MM. OR = Odds Ratio. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .001$

Conclusion

This paper uses polynomial logistic regression to look into gender differences in research method usage according to author-gender combinations in LIS. We discover that solo female authors are more likely to employ communication and observation-related methods including Interview, Observation, and Questionnaire. Most methods are more likely to be used by FM teams than by MM and FF teams. A deeper understanding of gender and method usage requires research in a wider range of areas.

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